

VIBRATION ATTENUATION PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID COMPOSITE LATTICE SANDWICH PANELS COMBINED WITH HIGH DAMPING MATERIALS

J. S. Yang^{1*}, W. M. Zhang¹, and L. Z. Wu¹

¹ Key Laboratory of Advanced Ship Materials and Mechanics, College of Aerospace and Civil Engineering, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, PR China

* Corresponding author (yangjinshui@hrbeu.edu.cn)

Keywords: composite; sandwich panels; damping ; pyramidal truss cores

ABSTRACT

Hybrid composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels combined with multiple damping configurations are fabricated in this work. Modal and quasi-static compressive tests are carried out to investigate the damping and stiffness efficiency of the candidate structures. Experimental results show that such structures combined with damping materials would significantly improve the damping loss efficiency but decrease simultaneously the stiffness efficiency in varying degrees compared with the bare hybrid sandwich panels. In order to evaluate the compatible effect of total damping and stiffness efficiency of the present sandwich structures, a synthetic evaluation criterion is developed, which shows that bare sandwich panels filled with hard polyurethane foam (B-II-HPF) and soft polyurethane foam (B-II-SPF) can yield the best performance up to 2-4 times higher than the base hybrid sandwich panels. It is also shown that multiple patch damping treatments based on the FE-MSE approach are suitable and effective to further improve the total damping efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures generally consist of two thin face sheets bonded to a thick and lightweight core with any topological configurations using adhesive interface layers. For the high strength and stiffness to weight ratio, sandwich structures are widely used in many engineering applications including aircraft, automotive and marine industries [1]. Unfortunately, lightweight and stiff materials and structures are usually associated with relatively low damping [2-4] which can cause early mechanical damage caused by resonant vibration. The method of constrained layer damping (CLD) that was first proposed by Kerwin [3] has been proven effective in vibration suppression. In addition, filling of the core voids with foam or viscoelastic material have been also investigated in order to improve the structural damping loss factors [4-6]. However, the insertion of the damping material inside the face sheets and core of the sandwich panel increases the extra mass which is undesired and always significantly changes the dynamic properties. To tackle this problem and its related field, many optimization techniques such as Genetic Algorithm, Moving Asymptotes method, were successfully adopted [7]. To date, most of the research about structural damping optimization focused on simple CLD beams, panels and shells using theory and numerical simulations, which usually lack of experimental verification. However, to the authors' knowledge, there are only few reports on vibration damping optimization of composite sandwich structures with honeycomb cores, and much less for complicated lattice truss cores.

In this study, modal and compression tests are carried out to investigate the vibration damping and stiffness efficiency of hybrid composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels combined with multiple damping configurations, respectively. Furthermore, based on the modal strain energy approach, multiple patch damping treatments are implemented in the base structures using the validated Finite Element (FE) models that aim at obtaining the highest damping loss factor using the minimal mass without any stiffness penalty.

2 FABRICATION APPROACHES

Hybrid composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels without and with combinations of high lossy materials are manufactured based on the hot mould press approach. The mechanical properties of the used materials are listed in Table 1. The fabricated specimens are shown in Fig.1.

Table 1 The mechanical properties of the used materials

Property	Symbol	LS-3K [7]	2A12-T4	VDS	HPF	SPF	SR
Young's modulus (Mpa)	E_1, E_2	46700	68700	20.69	61.50	1.25	1200
Shear modulus (Mpa)	G_{12}	3600	25400	—	—	—	—
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.30	0.32	0.47	0.32	0.27	0.48
Density (kg/m ³)	ρ	1523.3	2687	1650	73.22	114.9	789.1

Fig.1 (a) The bare hybrid composite pyramidal truss sandwich panel, (b) the repeating unit cell (RUC), (c) hybrid sandwich panel filled with polyurethane foam, (d) hybrid sandwich panel filled with silicone rubber, (e) hybrid sandwich panel inserted with viscoelastic damping sheets and filled with polyurethane foam.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Modal testing

To understand the effect of the high lossy materials on the structural vibration damping, the specimens of hybrid composite sandwich panels are tested by using the DEWETRON dynamic

signal analyzers [7], where the impulse impact method is adopted via the single-input multi-output analysis method.

Fig. 2 (a) The experimental apparatus of modal tests and (b) the typical frequency response functions of a bare hybrid sandwich panel.

3.2 Quasi-static compression

After modal tests, all the specimens are subjected to quasi-static compression tests with a nominal displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min to determine their energy absorption characteristics according to the standardized test method, ASTM C365/C365M-05 [8].

4 SIMULATION

In this section, a commercial finite element code ABAQUS 6.13 is used to model such hybrid composite sandwich panels. Firstly, 3D solid elements are adopted to establish the FEM model of hybrid composite sandwich panels, then, a frequency extraction procedure using the Lanczos eigensolver is implemented and the natural frequencies, mode shapes and the mechanical properties such as modal strain energy magnitude, stress components, strain components and volume of each element can be obtained by the data post-processing.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.3 (a) gives the frequency responses of bare composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels (specimen B) by experimental modal testing in a range of first several predominant frequencies. It can be found that, the natural frequencies increase with the increase of face sheet thickness. It also can be observed that the amplitudes of the peaks slightly decline with the increase of face sheet thickness. It seems that appropriately increasing the thickness of the face sheets can effectively improve the structural damping. The reason is mainly that increasing the thickness would greatly enhance the structural total stiffness. It also can be observed that the amplitudes of the peaks slightly decline with the increase of face sheet thickness. It seems that appropriately increasing the thickness of the face sheets can effectively improve the structural damping. The comparisons of frequency responses of

specimen B with combinations of high lossy materials are shown in Fig.3(b). The amplitudes of the peaks decline significantly after adding high damping materials, even some of the response amplitudes significantly diminish which leads to the disappearance of the peak values.

Fig. 3 Comparison of frequency responses. (a) Specimens B with different face sheet thickness, (b) Specimen B with different combination of high lossy materials.

Similarly, we also investigate the compressive responses of the present sandwich structures shown in Fig.4. The experimental results indicated that increasing the face sheet thickness and filling high damping materials in the void spaces of the truss cores has little effect on the total compressive stiffness but would relatively affect the strength compared to the unfilled structures. However, inserting the VDS inside the middle layer of the upper and lower face sheets obviously decreases total compressive stiffness. The reason is that the VDS layer is more easily to be deformed than filled structures combined with truss members, which play the role of strengthening the structures.

Fig. 4 Comparison of compressive responses. (a) Specimens B-II-HPF with different face sheet thickness, (b) and (c) Specimens B with different combination of high lossy materials (Tf =0.8mm).

To further explore the additional mass on the influence of the total stiffness, the compressive stiffness efficiency E_s of such hybrid sandwich panels with different combination of high lossy materials is shown in Fig.5 (b). It is easy to understand that the bare specimen B possesses the highest stiffness efficiency, followed by the specimen B-II-HPF and B-II-SPF, until the B-III-SPF because of their lower specific modulus. In conclusion, Fig.5 (c) gives the comprehensive evaluation criteria of specimen B with different combinations of high lossy materials. It is clearly revealed that the specimen B-II-HPF and B-II-SPF occupy the highest values with the average error. It means that such two structural configurations can significantly improve modal damping using least redundant mass without any stiffness loss.

Fig. 5 Comparison of (a) Damping loss efficiency, (b) Stiffness efficiency and (c) Evaluation criteria of specimen B with different combination of high lossy materials ($T_f=0.8\text{mm}$).

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, modal and compression tests are carried out to investigate the vibration damping and stiffness efficiency of hybrid composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels combined with multiple damping configurations, respectively. Experimental results show that increasing of the face sheet thickness would effectively increase the natural frequencies and appropriately improve the structural damping. Compared with the bare hybrid sandwich panels, such structures combined with damping materials would significantly improve the damping loss efficiency but decrease the stiffness efficiency in varying degrees simultaneously. According to the comprehensive evaluation, specimen B-II-HPF and B-II-SPF can yield the best performance among all the candidate specimens.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work was supported by the National Science Foundation of China under Grant No. 11802070, and the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities under Grant No. 3072019CFM0202.

REFERENCES

- [1] Evans A G, Hutchinson J W, Fleck N A, et al. The topological design of multifunctional cellular metals. *Pro Mater Sci* 2001; 46: 309-27.
- [2] George T, Deshpande V S, Sharp K, et al. Hybrid core carbon fiber composite sandwich panels: Fabrication and mechanical response. *Compos Struct* 2014, 108: 696-710.
- [3] Kerwin Jr E M. Damping of flexural waves by a constrained viscoelastic layer. *J Acoust Soc Am* 1959, 31(7): 952-962.
- [4] Maheri M R, Adams R D. Finite-element prediction of modal response of damped layered composite panels. *Compos Sci Technol* 1995, 55(1): 13-23.
- [5] Yang J S, Xiong J, Ma L, et al. Vibration and damping characteristics of hybrid carbon fiber composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels with viscoelastic layers. *Compos Struct* 2013, 106: 570-580.
- [6] Yang J S, Xiong J, Ma L, et al. Modal response of all-composite corrugated sandwich cylindrical shells. *Compos Sci Technol* 2015, 115: 9-20.
- [7] Yang J S, Ma L, Schmidt R, et al. Hybrid lightweight composite pyramidal truss sandwich panels with high damping and stiffness efficiency. *Compos Struct* 2016, 148:85-96.